

**MINTAQADA ZAMONAVIY FAN, TA'LIM VA TARBIYANING
DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI**

**ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN SCIENCE, EDUCATION
AND TRAINING IN THE REGION**

**АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ,
ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ В РЕГИОНЕ**

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ANALYSIS OF SOME PROBLEMATIC SITUATIONS IN UZBEK

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mualliflar o'zbek tilining til korpusini yaratish bilan bog'liq masalalarni muhokama qiladilar. Shu munosabat bilan, korpus tilidagi tillarni o'rganish, turli xil milliy korpus va o'zbek tilining korpusini yaratishdagi qiyinchiliklar kabi masalalar batafsil tahlil qilinadi va bir qator takliflar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: korpus, korpus lingvistikasi, korpus lug'ati, korpus dasturi, milliy korpus.

Аннотация: В этой статье авторы обсуждают вопросы, связанные с созданием языкового корпуса узбекского языка. В этой связи тщательно анализируются такие вопросы, как сбор языковых единиц в корпусе, различные национальные проблемы и трудности с созданием корпуса узбекского языка, и предлагается ряд предложений.

Ключевые слова: корпус, корпусная лингвистика, словарь корпуса, корпусная программа, национальный корпус.

Abstract: In this article, authors discuss the issues related to the creation of language corpus of Uzbek Language. In this regard, the matter, such as the collection of language units in the corpus, different national corpus and difficulties in creating the corpus of Uzbek language, are thoroughly analyzed and a number of proposals are suggested.

Keywords: corpus, corpus linguistics, corpus vocabulary, corpus program, national corpus.

As current information technologies are developing at high rates day-by-day, national language content plays a key role in preserving the identity of each nation. At the same time, we need to develop further Uzbek language studies, new researches in linguistics, modern methods of studying and teaching the Uzbek language. Corpus linguistics arises a major factor in this sense.

The word “corpus” means “body”, “part”, “fragment”. Corpus linguistics is one of the large parts of computational linguistics. The purpose of the corpus linguistics is to integrate knowledge and theories about all linguistic sections into a single system. And corpus is a set of the comprehensive database of languages and bibliographic texts attached to the search program to identify the features of the body language units.

The corpus of languages is one of the most influential tools to solve all the issues of the surveys and practical tasks of the language. Gries considers corpus linguistics as a paradigm and states: “Corpus Linguistics has become a major methodological paradigm in practical and theoretical linguistics over the last decades.” McEnergy, Wilson, Meyer, Becker, and Pearson define it as the following: “Corpus Linguistics is the style and method of studying the use of language.” As we can assume, the corpus can be both a source for learning a language and a method of studying it at the same time. Every word in the corpus is individually applied, including the following information through the corpus program:

- 1) The entire set of different language units in different contexts;
- 2) Positions and variants of language units in the lexicography;
- 3) The list of words that can be combined with the chosen word;
- 4) Frequency or statistics of the same word usage by the same author;
- 5) Core and metaphorical meanings of a word;
- 6) Hidden capabilities of word usage;
- 7) The state of the application of words in different periods of the language development;
- 8) Ability to connect with affixes;
- 9) Exact equivalents of a word in foreign languages;
- 10) The scope of word use on the local regions;
- 11) orthoepic and spelling rules in audio scripts and so on.

Creation of the national body of the Uzbek language is the main task nowadays. To create the body, not only linguists but also literary critics, programmers, librarians, historians, psychologists, sociologists, translators need to work collaboratively. The advantage of the corpus is that it can be utilized by everybody from all professions in general. For instance, when editors work on the texts, they will look for words which are stylistically suitable for the texts and choose one of them from the synonymic line appearing on the special program screen in order to make the text more attractive. Or, researchers can easily find any information about the language and linguistic background which requires a long time to be found through the corps program. Another advantage of the corpus is

that it saves time. To do this, any user just goes to the application and press the “Search” button. Language related information will be displayed on the screen.

Today, unless we create a computerized form of Uzbek language, it may appear in the list of languages that are in danger of extinction. Corpus linguistics serves as one of the key solutions to this problem. It should also be noted that if the Uzbek language corpus is created, it will be one of the biggest events in our linguistics. Particularly, the eternity of the language is preserved, comprising the features that make it easier to learn and teach.

The first corpus in the world was created at the University of Brown in the USA in 1961. Later, in the USSR, corpus vocabulary which had a million words was created. The British, German, and Russian languages have their own national corpus, including the largest German national corpus. That's because this corpus possesses 3.5 million words. Not all of these words are currently used in German and German linguists have also included national most used terms and expressions in ancient times. That is why the German national corpus has reached the highest level of body coverage in the world. In the family of Turkic languages the Osmanli Turk, Uighur, Crimean-Tatar national corpus were created. Linguist scholars from Kazakhstan and Tajikistan are doing their research on the creation of their own national corpus.

There are about 50 projects in the world that are mainly in Indian-European languages. Creation of the language corpus requires a great deal of research from scientists and there is theoretical knowledge on the creation of the Uzbek national body. However, scientific research carrying out at present in practice cannot be considered available. One of the main reasons for this is that the government does not allocate necessary funds to conduct corpus research; there are no corpus laboratories and few corpus researchers. Problems with the formation of the corpus are related to history and archeology, source studies, study of ancient writers, as well as to the richness of the Uzbek language in synonyms, metaphorical units, and especially in dialects. Thus, creating a corpus language according to the above factors leads to a number of difficulties. In the corpus of the language, there is also given dialects. However, the Uzbek language dialects are various. For instance, in the example of the Surkhandarya region, the dialects of the neighboring villages differ from each other. Facts such as lack of well-descriptive language dictionaries, lack of vocabulary textures, excellent dialectological research, which meets today's requirements, including the capability to use dialect-based words in the corpus and to find their literary language alternatives in the foreign languages require special research. This, in turn, also entails prolongation of time for the creation of the language corpus. Among the Turkic languages, the Uzbek language is

distinguished by its abundant synonymic and metaphorical entries. In the corpus, there is given a dominant word and its other synonyms and they take special emphasis on the meaning, style, use, expression, and task in the synonymic line. As there are so many connections that they cannot be translated directly into the foreign language, or they do not exist in that language, a bilingual corpus is more preferable and effective. This also affects the efficiency of the creation of the corpus.

According to the above facts that we have discussed, we propose the followings:

- 1) Provision of state support for the creation of the national corpus of the Uzbek language with the help of leading specialists;
- 2) Establishing a corpus lab and research center;
- 3) Intensifying the creation of the national corpus of the Uzbek language through the experience of the existing national corpus;
- 4) The involvement of students interested in this field who are studying at the Higher Education Institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the process of creating corpus;
- 5) Creating a bilingual corpus. This is an easy-to-use corpus for translators, who want to learn Uzbek;
- 6) Creating an online corpus. This will give everybody the advantages that will allow them to get information, which is not given in the corpus, through educational websites;
- 7) The inclusion of the audio format of the information together with written one in the corpus. The main purpose of this corpus is to teach Uzbek language and its spelling and orthoepic rules to those who are eager to learn the language and to convey the exact pronunciation of the word to the listener.

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